

Chemical Investigation of *Pyrus Communis*, Linn.

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Pyrus communis, Linn. (Fam. Rosaceae) is a medium-sized tree, growing abundantly in the temperate Himalayan region. The present work deals with the isolation of three different compounds from the bark of *Pyrus communis*, Linn. It has been possible to identify friedelin (0.5%) and *epi*-friedelinol (0.1%) from the petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) extract and β -sitosterol (0.04%) from the chloroform extract of the bark.

Air-dried powdered bark was extracted successively with petroleum (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform, and ethanol (90%). The light petroleum fraction, when concentrated to a small volume, provided a faintly yellow crystalline mass. The chloroform fraction afforded a small amount of a residue and the ethanolic fraction contained only a negligible amount of a material. Chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina of the product, obtained from the light petroleum extract, furnished two distinct crystalline fractions.

Fraction(I), crystallised from methanol, m.p. 254-56°; $[\alpha]_D^{27} - 29^\circ$ (CHCl₃), responded to the Burchard-Lieberman reaction; it did not exhibit any colour with tetranitromethane. Mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of friedelin¹⁻³ remained undepressed. (Found: C, 84.56; H, 11.66. Calc. for C₃₀H₅₀O: C, 84.50; H, 11.74%). The oxime crystallised from benzene, m.p. 292°; mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of friedelin oxime, 292°. (Found: C, 81.42; H, 11.30. Calc. for C₃₀H₅₁ON: C, 81.63; H, 11.56%).

Fraction(II), m.p. 275-76° (crystallised from benzene) also responded to the Burchard-Lieberman reaction and showed no coloration with tetranitromethane. It did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample³⁻⁴ of *epi*-friedelinol. (Found: C, 84.38; H, 12.41. Calc. for C₃₀H₅₂O: C, 84.11; H, 12.23%). It furnished an acetate, m.p. 284-86°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 33.8^\circ$ (CHCl₃). (Found: C, 81.58; H, 11.6. Calc. for C₃₂H₅₄O₂: C, 81.7; H, 11.48%).

The chloroform extract on being subjected to chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina yielded only one crystalline fraction, m.p. 137-38°. It responded to the Burchard-Lieberman reaction; it was crystallised from methanol. The compound was acetylated and the product crystallised from acetone, m.p. 126°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} - 40.5^\circ$ (CHCl₃). The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of the acetate of β -sitosterol remained unchanged. (Found: C, 81.53; H, 11.55. Calc. for C₃₁H₅₂O₂: C, 81.52; H, 11.48%).

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